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Report

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1. Introduction

During the most recent reporting period, transparency regarding **compliance with Commitment 17**¹ by the entities that signed the 2022 Code of Practice on Disinformation (CoP) —officially transformed into the binding [Code of Conduct on Disinformation](#) in 2025, which became a key benchmark for Digital Services Act (DSA) compliance,— **has markedly declined**. This deliverable compiles the reports submitted by the CoP signatories to the <https://disinfocode.eu/> platform in **September 2025**. These reports correspond to the **evaluation period from 1 January to 30 June, 2025**. It has been observed that, although signatories are expected to **promote media literacy, user empowerment, and cooperation with public institutions**, the information disclosed in their most recent reports shows an **increasing lack of detail and measurable outcomes**.

Furthermore, this trend suggests a **growing reluctance among Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) and Very Large Online Search Engines (VLOSEs)** to maintain their commitment to the Code's educational and societal dimensions. This is the **third deliverable prepared by IBERIFIER, the EDMO hub monitoring disinformation in Portugal and Spain**. The previous deliverables included **recommendations and proposed measures**. In **Deliverable 5.1** (Moreno-Castro & Paisana et al., 2024), general measures were proposed; in **Deliverable 5.2** (Moreno-Castro & Paisana et al., 2025), specific measures were outlined for each signatory; and in this **Deliverable 5.3** we continue to provide tailored recommendations for each of the signatories. In addition, in this deliverable, **two signatories are identified as not having subscribed to Commitment 17 (LinkedIn and Bing)**. Consequently, the analysis focuses on assessing **their visibility and coverage in the media**, particularly within **daily general information outlets**.

In this sense, this decline in transparency in reporting coincided with a period of intense public scrutiny. Throughout 2024 and 2025, Spanish and Portuguese media outlets published numerous articles highlighting users' **growing exposure to harmful and misleading content** across signatures such as YouTube, TikTok, Meta, and Google. Press investigations repeatedly underscored the **erosion of user protection** in the European information ecosystem and the **limited accountability** of major technology companies. The coverage highlighted a widening gap between the public commitments of signatories to the CoP and their tangible actions to strengthen users' digital resilience.

Simultaneously, calls intensified within the European Union for the **DSA** to be enforced with greater rigour. Policymakers and civil society actors have urged the European Commission to ensure that the DSA's obligations translate into **concrete**

¹ Commitment 17 of the Code of Conduct on Disinformation states: “In light of the European Commission’s initiatives in the area of media literacy, including the new Digital Education Action Plan, relevant Signatories commit to continue and strengthen their efforts in the area of media literacy and critical thinking, also with the aim to include vulnerable groups.” This commitment is operationalized through three specific measures, which are detailed in the Code.

accountability mechanisms that compel signatures to meet their commitments under the Code. This regulatory momentum reflects growing frustration with voluntary compliance and the perception that self-regulation alone is insufficient to address the systemic risks posed by disinformation and algorithmic manipulation.

In this context, the present report offers an updated assessment of the performance of VLOP and VLOSE signatories under **Commitment 17**, focusing on their actions, or lack thereof, to promote **media literacy and critical thinking among European users**. Furthermore, the analysis paid particular attention to media coverage in Spain and Portugal, where recent developments have amplified concerns about the **disparity between communication outlets and public responsibility** in the fight against disinformation (Cardoso et al., 2025; Sierra et al., 2025)).

1.1. Objectives

1. To **evaluate a sample of the VLOPs and VLOSEs' initial compliance** and engagement with the Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation, focusing on their efforts to empower users via Commitment 17.
2. To **recommend concrete and specific measures** for improving the implementation of the Code of Practice on Disinformation, with **a particular focus** on enhancing the effectiveness of Commitment 17 related to media literacy and their localised implementation in **Portugal and Spain**.
3. To **examine media coverage** in Portugal and Spain to determine whether news has been published relating to the companies that have signed the Code of Practice on Disinformation, and in particular concerning Commitment 17, during the reporting period covered by the signatories.

1.2. Methodology

In line with the methodology of IBERIFIER Plus' report² (Deliverable D5.2) released in June 2025, the assessment presented in this report (Deliverable D5.3) follows a standardised and collaborative methodology developed in coordination with the methodological subgroup, which includes representatives from each European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) Hub. This subgroup met several times to discuss and harmonise the assessment approach, ensuring a consistent, transparent, and fair evaluation process across all participating hubs. A key feature of the methodology is the use of **double coding** for each assessment. This means that two independent

² Moreno Castro, C., Paisana, M., Falcó-Moreno, N., Vázquez Herrero, J., Azurmendi, A., Calvo, D., Pérez-Seijo, S., Moreno, J., Cano-Orón, L., Negreira Rey, M. C., Rodríguez-Vázquez, A.-I., Sixto-García, J., Cabrera García-Ochoa, Y., Vizoso, Á., Sánchez-Hualde, A., & Salaverria, R. (2025). *IBERIFIER - Assessment of VLOPs (Very Large Online Platforms) and VLOSEs (Very Large Online Search Engines). Signatory Reports for the Strengthened Code of Practice on Disinformation. Report No. 2*. IBERIFIER. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15753700>

reviewers evaluated each signatory's report, comparing interpretations and resolving discrepancies through discussion at **the first level** within the same partner team. The second level was **intercode** among different partners. At the end, 11 coders agree on the evaluation score. This approach enhances the objectivity of the findings and reduces the risk of individual bias. The combination of evidence-based and qualitative assessment ensures that the report records compliance in formal terms and critically reflects on the **effectiveness** and **strategic relevance** of the signatories' actions in combating disinformation and fostering a more informed public. The assessment focused on three core dimensions:

1. **Quality of the report:** This criterion considers how clearly and systematically the signatories present their activities. It includes the organisation of the report, the clarity of language, the use of structured formats, and the overall accessibility of the information for external reviewers. A three-point Likert scale (1 = Poor, 2 = Partial, 3 = Good, 4 = Not applicable) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).
2. **Evidence provided by the signatories:** This dimension evaluates whether the described actions are supported by concrete documentation or data. Evaluators assessed the credibility, relevance, and sufficiency of the evidence presented, including links to relevant resources, examples of implemented tools, training materials, and statistical indicators. A three-point Likert scale (1 = Poor, 2 = Partial, 3 = Good, 4 = Not applicable) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).
3. **Impact of the actions implemented:** The final dimension assesses the extent to which the actions undertaken by the signatories align with the goals of **Commitment 17**, which focuses on **enhancing media literacy**. This includes developing digital skills, deploying educational tools, targeting vulnerable populations, and implementing broader awareness-raising strategies. The assessment also considers how well these actions are adapted to regional or national contexts, particularly relevant in the Iberian context of Spain and Portugal, where media literacy needs and disinformation dynamics may differ from other parts of Europe. A five-point Likert scale (1 = Very Poor, 2 = Poor, 3 = Fair, 4 = Good, 5 = Excellent) was used, following the EDMO standardisation and guidelines (Cesarini et al., 2024; EDMO, 2024; EFCSN, 2024; Botan & Meyer, 2025).
4. **Media context:** Analysis of how news outlets in Portugal and Spain reported on the signatories' actions and engagement under **Commitment 17** of the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**, focusing on the tone, frequency, and framing of coverage during the reporting period. The methodology applied for this descriptive analysis involved a targeted media search in **Portugal and Spain**, focusing on identifying coverage related to companies that have signed the *Code of Practice on Disinformation*, particularly in connection with

Commitment 17, during the reporting period covered by the signatories (from **1 January to 30 June 2025**). For the **Spanish media**, searches were conducted using the **MyNews** platform. In Portugal, **Google News** was used to search for relevant media coverage in the same period. Without geographic limitations, we also found relevant coverage about the topic in Brazil, in Brazilian portuguese. Both researcher teams employed **Boolean operators** designed to capture relevant content. The search criteria included: a) News stories referring to the different signatories analysed in this report (Google Search, YouTube, LinkedIn, TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, Bing); The time frame between **1 January and 30 June 2025**; and c) the exact text: **“código de buenas prácticas”** in Spanish and **“Código de boas-práticas”** in Portuguese.

2. Deep assessment for the signatory Google Search

2.1. Media context: How did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover Google's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

During the first half of 2025, Spanish media coverage portrays **Google** as one of the most significant signatories yet among the **most resistant to fulfilling its obligations** under the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**. **Its withdrawal from EU commitments, the present lack of transparency in content verification, and the absence of media literacy programs point to a clear violation of Article 17**, which focuses on education and public awareness in combating misinformation.

Overall, the press portrays Google as a company that **prioritises its corporate strategy and market interests over its social and regulatory responsibilities**, thereby deepening institutional distrust in its role within the European digital landscape.

The most relevant headlines on Google Search in Portugal and Spanish dailies

1. **“Bruxelas processa Portugal por não aplicar totalmente lei de serviços digitais”** (*Brussels sues Portugal for failing to fully implement digital services law*). Source: Rádio Renascença. May 7th 2025. **The European Commission has brought Portugal before the Court of Justice of the EU** for failing to implement the Digital Services Act fully. **Although Portugal appointed a national coordinator, it did not grant the necessary supervisory powers nor establish the required sanctioning rules.** The country is among several Member States that have not ensured full enforcement of the regulation aimed at improving oversight, transparency, and the removal of illegal content. The case forms part of the May infringements package, which also highlights shortcomings in the transposition of the cybersecurity directive.
2. **“UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital”** (*UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital*). Source: Poder360br. February 14th 2025. The EU announced on 13 February 2025 that the Code of Practice on Disinformation will be integrated into the Digital Services Act (DSA). **The updated framework introduces measures to reduce financial incentives for spreading false information and to strengthen transparency in political advertising**, according to EFE. Participation remains voluntary, but compliance will now be subject to audits. **Since 2018, forty-two companies have joined the initiative, including Google, Meta, Microsoft, and TikTok. Elon Musk's platform X remains the only major platform not participating.**
3. **“Facebook, Instagram e WhatsApp lideram queixas sobre serviços digitais**

em Portugal” (*Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp lead complaints about digital services in Portugal*). Source: Tek Notícias, Sapo. June 16th 2025. In the first quarter of the year, **ANACOM received 27 complaints about digital services, of which Google accounted for 8%.**

4. **ANACOM also forwarded two complaints to the Digital Services Coordinators of Ireland and the Netherlands, indicating possible breaches of the Digital Services Act by platforms based in those countries.** As Portugal’s designated Digital Services Coordinator since February 2024, ANACOM emphasises that platforms must provide clear reasons for any account or content moderation decisions and maintain an internal complaint-handling system that is timely, non-discriminatory, and non-arbitrary. Users may submit complaints to ANACOM, which will assess and, if necessary, forward them to the relevant national coordinator.
5. **“Google tensa la cuerda con Europa: no seguirá las normas de verificación de contenido en YouTube ni en búsquedas”** (*Google tightens the rope with Europe: it refuses to follow EU content verification rules for YouTube and Search*). Source: Genbeta, January 18, 2025. The article reports that Google has decided **not to fully implement the content verification measures required by the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**, arguing that such requirements **restrict freedom of expression and harm the company’s competitiveness**. This decision represents a **significant step back from Google’s previous commitments** and has raised concerns in Brussels about a **systematic breach** of the Code. The report also notes that Google’s **internal verification system lacks transparency**, making independent oversight of disinformation control nearly impossible.
6. **“Bea Talegón: Google y YouTube hacen un corte de mangas a la UE por su política de censura”** (*Google and YouTube defy the EU over its “censorship” policy*) Source: *El Nacional*, January 18, 2025. This opinion piece highlights the **tensions between Google and the European Commission** regarding content moderation policies. Google argues that the new European requirements **amount to censorship**, while the EU insists that platforms must **assume social responsibility** in tackling disinformation. The article underscores the Code’s central challenge: **balancing freedom of expression with factual accountability**.
7. **“Europa debe fijar un modelo de negocio que priorice el bienestar de los usuarios sobre la rentabilidad económica”** (*Europe must design a business model that puts users’ well-being before profit*). Source: *El País*, May 2, 2025 – Opinion column by Enrique Goñi (*Fundación Hermes*). The author criticises Google for **abandoning its commitments under the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation, even as the European Commission seeks to make it legally binding** through the **Digital Services Act (DSA)**. The article notes that although Google was once a **key actor in combating disinformation**, it has

now **withdrawn from compliance**, claiming that these standards interfere with its market strategy. This retreat, according to the piece, **worsens the spread of misinformation** and **erodes public trust**, weakening the EU's verification and transparency framework.

8. **“Los impulsores de la ley europea de IA, preocupados por los intentos de la UE de rebajar las obligaciones a las big tech”** (*AI law advocates in Europe express concern over attempts to ease Big Tech's obligations*). Source: *El Español*, March 25, 2025. The article highlights **concerns from experts and lawmakers** about growing pressure from tech giants like Google to loosen regulatory requirements on algorithmic transparency and disinformation control. Analysts warn that **watering down these obligations could render the EU's Code of Practice ineffective**, undermining its capacity to safeguard the integrity of the online information ecosystem.

1. Withdrawal from the EU Code of Practice commitments

Google has **stepped back from fully applying the Code** precisely as the European Commission seeks to formalise it under the DSA.

This move **breaks the collaborative framework** that had been built to coordinate international action against disinformation.

2. Rejection of independent content verification

Google has chosen **not to rely on external fact-checking organisations**, thereby **reducing transparency and reliability** across its information ecosystem (YouTube, Search, News).

The lack of independent verification exposes users to **systemic disinformation risks** embedded in its recommendation and search algorithms.

3. Absence of media literacy initiatives (Article 17)

Throughout the first half of 2025, **no major educational or awareness initiatives** in Spain led by Google were identified that aimed to promote media literacy or digital verification. This constitutes a **breach of Article 17**, which mandates active cooperation with institutions and media organisations to **foster public resilience to misinformation**.

4. Conflict between profitability and social responsibility

The analysed articles emphasise that Google **prioritises its business model and market dominance** over compliance with EU transparency and ethics standards. This stance **undermines public media literacy efforts and weakens accountability mechanisms** envisioned by the EU framework.

After examining how Spanish- and Portuguese-language outlets framed Commitment 17, the table below outlines Google Search's performance in meeting the requirements of the CoP.

Table 1. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Google Search

Signatory: Google Search	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	1- poor
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	2- partial
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	1- very poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	2- poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- adequate, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

2.2. Quality of response assessment

Google Search highlights three main actions:

1. Transparency-focused tools from previous reports. Features like “About This Result” (menu icon), help users to understand and evaluate information; “About this image” offers users contextual details about search results (allows users to see more information about the source, to find what others on the web have said about a site, and to learn more about the topic or, in the case of images, helps users to detect whether it has been created using Google’s AI tools or not). **These sections are well-explained and include links to explore the tool further. Conversely, “Content Advisory Notices” are less detailed and lack direct links to additional information or external sources.**

2. Funding. The company provides **support to various organisations that promote diversity** and inclusion. However, none of these recipients seems to be based in Portugal or Spain, indicating unequal support for Southern European countries. Specifically, there are four grants -shared Google Search-YouTube- that appear to be new in the period January-June 2025

- **GLOBSEC** –AI content recognition, and personalised learning to

educate users on civic topics) \$103,220.

- **Social Incubator**-AI-Powered civic education platform that offers a suite of tools for digital literacy training
- **Parlons Démocratie**, which helps teachers to deliver better civic education, and \$102,640
- **The CyberPeace** Institute's support for European civil society organisations (CSOs) to combat cyber-attacks and disinformation by using AI for actionable insights and collective intelligence is relatively low at \$103,060.

3. Educational initiatives. The Super Searchers Program has reportedly engaged 666 librarians. This project was also introduced and detailed in earlier reports.

Although **the activities reported seem adequate, they are the same as in the previous report (except for the four grants described)**. In addition, they don't report intentions to create new features or run new campaigns to boost media literacy, nor do they intend to implement those initiatives in the Iberian context through local/national action. The activities are described with insufficient detail regarding the objectives they pursue and how they can contribute to improving users' media literacy.

2.3. Verification of reported information

Regarding tools, the report provides a comprehensive set of indicators to contextualise transparency measures at the local level. Specifically, it includes an "impression proportion estimate" of content advisories and the "number of times" users use the option related to this content and image. These metrics collectively offer substantial quantitative data to interpret the impact of these transparency practices. Both Portugal and Spain have been assessed and reported with specific metrics.

Regarding funding, the document lists the allocated grants. However, it provides little detail about the specific projects supported or the outcomes achieved with these funds.

Lastly, in **educational terms**, the Super Searchers Program reportedly reached 666 librarians. Nonetheless, the report lacks further information: where these libraries are located, who the participants are, or what specific training activities were carried out. As a result, the program's scope and impact remain insufficiently described.

Metrics on impression proportion, 30 European countries, 1 January 2025 to 30 June 2025. This metric provides a percentage that shows how many times the alerts appeared on screen in relation to the total number of queries on topics that Google considered to fall into each of the two categories (content advisories for low-relevance results and content advisories for rapidly changing results). However, this proportion, although very low (0.097% in Portugal and 0.086% in Spain), does not provide

information on which content was included in these categories or on how users interacted with this content.

On the other hand, **Google provides two metrics expressed as total values** ('more about this page' and 'about this result'). **This data is useful, but it would be more valuable if it were contextualised in greater detail**, with information on how users interact with these features (clicks per impression, time spent reading per unique user, etc.).

On the other hand, **educational initiatives funded through grants** are not sufficiently described, as there is no information about the locations where the actions took place, the specific goals, or whether Google evaluated to assess the impact of the initiatives. It does not appear that any of the actions have occurred in the Iberian context, and the lack of details makes it difficult to assess their adequacy.

2.4. Evaluation of actions taken

Although the results of transparency-focused tools in this report seem slightly better than in previous studies, the overall impact of **the implemented tools remains limited**, reportedly below 1%. It seems necessary to implement new initiatives to increase awareness of the tools designed to implement them.

Additionally, many of these features operate only within specific environments, such as Google Search or Chrome, which restricts their broader applicability across platforms. Overall, the effectiveness of Google's transparency and literacy initiatives seems inadequate. The impact of transparency tools is still unclear. To boost the efficacy, **Google Search should develop clearer communication strategies** to improve user awareness and understanding of these tools, while increasing transparency in its funding and training processes.

The report provides information on financial allocations to various initiatives but offers no data on their outcomes or effectiveness. Additionally, the lack of detailed information about the outcomes of funding programs and training activities hinders a proper assessment of their results and social influence. The lack of evaluation metrics or follow-up reports makes **it difficult to determine whether the funded projects have met their objectives** or had measurable social impacts.

The **reported impact of the Super Searchers Program also remains unclear**. The documentation does not specify the nature of the training provided, the geographic distribution of participating libraries, or the profiles of the involved participants, as previously explained.

Finally, **there are no details related to collaboration with national partners in Spain or Portugal. Besides, there are no reports related to the national election in Portugal, despite the existence of a specific annexe for reporting national polls.**

All the measures and initiatives reported are global actions that, although they seem adequate, lack a national approach.

2.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

- Future initiatives should **aim for a broader geographic reach**, especially by strengthening their presence in Southern European countries, which currently seem underrepresented.
- It would be helpful if the **platform provided precise data on how users interact with the tools** Google offers to obtain contextual information.
- Google also reports **funding 121 projects in 28 European countries through the European Media and Information Fund**, but we couldn't find where the projects are located. It would be advisable to collaborate with Portuguese and Spanish entities to develop media literacy initiatives adapted to those countries, tailored for people at risk of social exclusion and minority groups.
- Seek ways to **collaborate with Spanish and Portuguese organisations** to promote media literacy initiatives tailored to the needs of these countries.

3. Deep assessment for the signatory YouTube

3.1. Media Context: How did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover YouTube's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

During the first half of 2025, Spanish media coverage of YouTube reflected **growing tension with the European Commission** over the enforcement of the **Code of Practice on Disinformation**. While the platforms reaffirmed their formal commitment, media reported highlighting **non-compliance in content verification** and a **lack of media literacy initiatives**, particularly concerning **Article 17**.

The most relevant headlines on YouTube in Portuguese and Spanish dailies

1. **“Bruxelas processa Portugal por não aplicar totalmente lei de serviços digitais”** (*Brussels sues Portugal for failing to fully implement digital services law*). Source: Rádio Renascença. May 7th 2025. **Although Portugal appointed a national coordinator, it did not grant the necessary supervisory powers nor establish the required sanctioning rules.** In this sense, YouTube is one of the platforms that gathers the most attention. The news pieces mainly cover instances of the voluntary adoption of measures thematically related to the EU's regulatory efforts, instances of complaints of platform behaviour by users and also, essential, **some national coverage on the fact that Portugal is not complying totally with EU law when it comes to the materialisation of these regulatory efforts.**
2. **“UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital”** (*UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital*). Source: Poder360br. February 14th 2025. The EU announced on 13 February 2025 that the Code of Practice on Disinformation will be integrated into the Digital Services Act (DSA). **The updated framework introduces measures to reduce financial incentives for spreading false information and to strengthen transparency in political advertising,** according to EFE. Participation remains voluntary, but compliance will now be subject to audits. **Since 2018, forty-two companies have joined the initiative, including Google, Meta, Microsoft, and TikTok. Elon Musk's platform X remains the only central platform not participating.**
3. **“Las grandes plataformas de internet se comprometen con la UE a un mayor escrutinio contra la incitación al odio”** (*Major internet platforms pledge greater scrutiny against hate speech under EU oversight*). Source: *Diario de Sevilla*, 21/01/2025. Reaffirmed the commitment of platforms like YouTube to the European Commission's **Code of Practice on Disinformation**, which

seeks to strengthen transparency and oversight of content that promotes hate or misinformation.

4. **“Google y YouTube hacen un corte de mangas a la UE por su política de censura”** (*Google and YouTube thumb their noses at the EU over its censorship policy*). Source: *El Nacional*, 18/01/2025. This news highlights **tensions between YouTube and the European Commission** over content moderation and alleged “censorship” policies. It notes that Google and YouTube believe some of the code’s requirements are excessive and infringe on freedom of expression.

5. **“Google tensa la cuerda con Europa: no seguirá las normas de verificación de contenido en YouTube ni en búsquedas”** (*Google tightens the rope with Europe: it won’t follow EU content verification rules for YouTube or search*). Source: *Genbeta*, 18/01/2025. Reports on Google’s decision not to fully implement the content verification measures required by the Code of Practice have raised concerns in Brussels about a **potential systematic breach of the code**, particularly regarding transparency and the control of misinformation.

Alerts on code violations

1. Resistance to verification standards: YouTube, under Google, has been criticised for **failing to fully comply with fact-checking and transparency standards** required by the code (Articles 5 and 17).

2. Conflict with the EU over alleged censorship: Some media outlets note that the company views EU measures as **restrictions on freedom of expression**. At the same time, the Commission insists that platforms have a social responsibility in tackling disinformation.

3. Lack of progress in media literacy (Article 17): No significant new initiatives by YouTube in Spain were observed during the first half of 2025 to enhance users’ media education, representing a **possible breach of Article 17**, which calls for concrete efforts in awareness, training, and cooperation with public institutions.

After examining how Spanish- and Portuguese-language outlets framed Commitment 17, the table below outlines YouTube's performance in meeting the CoP's requirements.

Table 2. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: YouTube

Signatory: YouTube Search	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	1- poor
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	1- poor
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	1- very poor
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	1- very poor

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- adequate, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

3.2. Quality of response assessment

The overall data provided by YouTube is insufficient. The signature reports a couple of initiatives, but they are not adequately documented. Besides, when analysing them, some questions arise that should be addressed and explained in detail:

1. Information panels: There is a **significant imbalance across countries** regarding the reach of the campaign. It would be necessary for the signature to provide data to analyse the reasons behind those differences and assess whether there is a way to expand the tool's reach. For instance, **it would be necessary to provide a ratio of interactions per user across countries, so we could compare countries or assess whether impressions in Portugal are undercounted relative to Spain.**

On the other hand, **the report does not detail how YouTube can guarantee that panels are consistently associated with relevant videos.** Therefore, it would be necessary to detail which systems are in place to ensure that panels are shown in all relevant videos and to explain whether panels are shown in all videos related to a specific topic or only in those where disinformation is believed to be present. In addition, it would strengthen the report's quality if the VLOP offered metrics beyond impressions, especially given that YouTube is very effective at identifying which content attracts the most attention and motivates action. It would be helpful if the platform provided more information in this regard. **Metrics such as click-through rates, clicks, average viewing time per session, etc., would be more accurate to assess the real impact of the information panels.**

2. Hit Pause campaign: The channel for the Hit Pause campaign has **only one new video published in the past six months, which is published in several languages.** The video addresses synthetic content generated by AI, a significant concern that the VLOP might want to explore given its major role as a content indexer and provider. Other than that, we find the same issues as with the information panels in measure 17.1. Even though the impressions appear to be similar in Spain and Portugal, in proportion to the internet user base in both countries, **deeper insights are needed**, as impressions are a poor KPI by themselves. **Other indicators are required, such as click-through rates and clicks.** The absence of appropriate metrics here is less understandable: the Hit Pause campaign is a YouTube channel, and it is widely known that YouTube provides state-of-the-art metrics for its content producers, per channel.

As stated by the platform: unlike Google Search, “no new implementation measures were employed in terms of service, new tools or new policies; the list of implementations is a transcript of the previous report”. In fact, it is said that “There are no plans for further measures in the next six months to improve the commitment, and therefore, they provide no information on such measures. It should be noted that the same report does show changes to Commitments other than Commitment 17, which are not considered here because they are out of the scope of this report.

3.3. Verification of reported information

The VLOP describes several initiatives but does not provide consistent details of the impact of existing initiatives (information panels, Hit Pause initiative) or of the expected effect of the grants and projects it supports in the context of Commitment 17.

Regarding the initiatives reported by YouTube:

1. **Information Panels - 1 Very poor** - for the reasons listed above (poor reporting and metrics), it is not possible to assess the initiative's effectiveness; also, no relevant information regarding the specific impact in Spain and Portugal. Impressions are an insufficient KPI in this instance.
2. **Hit Pause - 1 Very poor** - for the reasons listed above (poor reporting and metrics), it is not possible to assess the effectiveness of the initiative; also, no relevant information regarding the specific impact in Spain and Portugal. Impressions are an insufficient KPI in this instance.

3.4. Evaluation of actions taken

The **rating has been lowered to very poor because the reporting is the same as the last one, and there is no consideration for context** (e.g., the Portuguese general elections of March 2025) or for adapting the VLOP to that context. Furthermore, there is no mention of any AI initiatives, although it is known that the VLOP is interested in

the technology and its impacts. **There appears to be some reach for said initiatives, but there is little to no granularity in reported data, between and within countries.** For the reasons listed above, our ability to assess the impact of tools, activities and partnerships is limited.

Regarding collaboration with organisations, **YouTube should increase the number of organisations and experts it consults, as there is a wide range of organisations specialising in different facets of media and literacy.** There are plenty of partners to consider in Spain and Portugal, and research has shown that specific issues arise in the Iberian countries that could be actively mitigated by reaching out to experts knowledgeable about the realities on the ground. On the other hand, there is no ongoing direct collaboration between YouTube and IBERIFIER.

3.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

- **Improve the granularity of the metrics provided.** The data in the report does not allow for an accurate assessment of the platform's measures' actual impact. YouTube should **provide user interaction metrics** to assess the real impact of the initiatives accurately.
- Although the two **initiatives** reported appear adequate (the Hit the Pause campaign and the information panels), they are insufficiently described. **It must provide more details on the criteria** YouTube uses to activate information panels and the mechanism it applies to guarantee them. Information panels are displayed when necessary.
- The activities within the Hit the Pause campaigns are too limited; **more initiatives and better reporting** would improve the following reports.
- YouTube should contact local/national organisations in the Iberian countries (Portugal and Spain) to boost its strategy to improve media literacy, adapted to the specific contexts.

4. Deep assessment for the signatory LinkedIn

4.1. Media Context: How did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover LinkedIn's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

The most relevant headlines on LinkedIn in Portugal and Spanish dailies

1. **“Facebook, Instagram e WhatsApp lideram queixas sobre serviços digitais em Portugal”** (*Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp lead complaints about digital services in Portugal*). Source: Tek Notícias, Sapo. June 16th 2025. In the first quarter of the year, **ANACOM received 27 complaints about digital services, of which 11% were related to Microsoft (including LinkedIn and Bing)**.
2. **“Las grandes plataformas de internet se comprometen con la UE a un mayor escrutinio contra la incitación al odio”**(*Major internet platforms commit to increased EU oversight to curb hate speech*). **Sources:** *Diario de Sevilla, Diario de Cádiz, Diario de Jerez, Europa Sur, Málaga Hoy, Diario de Almería, Huelva Información, Granada Hoy, El Día de Córdoba* – January 21, 2025. This series of reports published by various outlets in the *Grupo Joly* media network highlights the **renewed commitment of major digital platforms, including LinkedIn (owned by Microsoft)**, to strengthen cooperation with the European Commission in the **fight against disinformation and hate speech**. The articles note that platforms adhering to the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation** have pledged to **increase transparency in their algorithms and content moderation policies**, in accordance with the **Digital Services Act (DSA)**. LinkedIn is listed among the platforms that have **formally reaffirmed their participation in the Code**, focusing efforts on **limiting the spread of professional misinformation and fraudulent content**, particularly in areas related to employment and corporate reputation.

The main alerts on possible code violations

1. Uneven implementation of the Code across platforms

Although LinkedIn has **reaffirmed its institutional commitment**, the news coverage does not mention **specific actions or educational campaigns** implemented in Spain during the first half of 2025 to promote media literacy. This suggests **formal compliance but limited substantive action** regarding **Article 17**, which requires active awareness and critical thinking programs for users.

2. Lack of transparency in professional content moderation

Analysts cited in technology outlets warn that LinkedIn **does not clearly disclose its moderation criteria** or provide detailed data on **how it addresses misinformation in professional or business-related content**, reducing public trust in the platform's integrity as a "verified information space."

3. Scarcity of media literacy initiatives (Article 17)

Unlike platforms with greater media visibility, such as YouTube or TikTok, **LinkedIn has not launched public campaigns on digital education in Spain** during the period analysed. **Article 17** of the Code requires collaboration between platforms, governments, and civil society organisations to **enhance public understanding of disinformation processes**, a goal that, according to the reviewed stories, **has not yet been achieved on LinkedIn**.

4. Risks linked to corporate disinformation and fake profiles

Despite LinkedIn's progress in **strengthening identity verification systems**, **cases of counterfeit or automated profiles continue to spread misleading information** related to job offers or investment opportunities. Such activity undermines the Code's principles, which call for **adequate safeguards to prevent information manipulation and ensure authenticity** across digital networks.

4.2. Statements from LinkedIn for not endorsing Commitment 17

LinkedIn withdrew from Commitment 17 under the new agreement signed in January 2025. As a result, it is not possible to assess the effectiveness of actions to empower users through media literacy measures. This decision was taken, surprisingly, after the previous IBERIFIER Plus report had highlighted the need to promote media-literacy initiatives more proactively in its Spanish and Portuguese markets.

Indeed, in its most recent report, covering actions undertaken in the second half of 2024, LinkedIn failed to address the Iberian hub's recommendations, providing limited evidence under tools and none for activities or partnerships. Consequently, the available documentation is insufficient to support a positive overall assessment of Commitment 17.

In the Subscription Document for LinkedIn Ireland Unlimited Company, signed on the 15th of January 2025³, **the company argues that the measures already in place are sufficient to limit misinformation and disinformation, according to its annual risk assessment. Yet, it offers no further clarification on which measures are**

³ Subscription Document for LinkedIn Ireland Unlimited Company. Available at <https://disinfocode.eu/subscriptionsforms/linkedin1759321508.pdf>

delivering results. It affirms its determination to “remove disinformation” and claims to have “a range of mitigations on point”, but the wording remains vague. While it contends—by reference to Article 34 of the Digital Services Act—that it is reasonable not to implement new actions, greater detail would be necessary to substantiate that position.

Its stated position is that it does not subscribe to these Measures because they are not proportionate to its disinformation risk profile under DSA Article 34 and would require interventions not reasonably tailored to the systemic risks it has identified; it maintains that current mitigations suffice and that it will continue to assess risks and implement tailored responses.

Finally, **the platform contends that the terms “media literacy” and “critical thinking” in the Commitment are open to interpretation**, calling them “vague” and “presenting audit challenges”. **However, these concepts are articulated in EU law**—see the European framework set out in the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD)—which provides a basis for operational definitions and auditability:

‘Media literacy’ refers to skills, knowledge and understanding that allow citizens to use media effectively and safely. To enable citizens to access information, use, critically assess, and create media content responsibly and safely, they need advanced media literacy skills. Media literacy should not be limited to learning about tools and technologies but should aim to equip citizens with the critical thinking skills required to exercise judgment, analyse complex realities and recognise the difference between opinion and fact. It is therefore necessary that both media service providers and video-sharing platforms providers, in cooperation with all relevant stakeholders, promote the development of media literacy in all sections of society, for citizens of all ages, and for all media and that progress in that regard is followed closely.

Although the European Commission’s definition of media literacy encompasses a wide range of possible activities, from the provision of contextual information and user guidance to formal training, partnerships with expert organisations, and public-awareness initiatives, this breadth should not be construed as a licence to abstain from action. On the contrary, it underscores an obligation to select and implement proportionate, evidence-informed measures appropriate to the platform’s risk profile and user base, and to document their design, reach, and impact with sufficient transparency to enable external scrutiny and accountability.

Regarding activities, the report does not document media-literacy awareness campaigns or programmes during the assessment period, nor does it supply reach, engagement, or participant figures.

5. Deep assessment for the signatory Bing

5.1. Media context: how did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover Bing's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

IBERIFIER researchers found no published news items about Bing during the analysis period in either Spain or Portugal.

5.2. Statements from Bing for not endorsing Commitment 17

In line with Microsoft's general position, **Bing also did not subscribe to Commitment 17**. It bases its position solely on the claim that “the measures on this commitment are not appropriately tailored to search engines or the manner in which disinformation risks may arise in search”⁴. However, no explanation is given as to why it is not adapted. It also states that “Microsoft will continue to support media literacy efforts consistent with the spirit of the Code”, but again, without evidence of how it is going to develop this.

During the reporting period, Microsoft announced two new strategic initiatives that mark a significant shift in its approach to the European digital landscape. In **April 2025**, the company launched the **European Digital Commitments**, a new programme framed as a long-term strategy for Europe. This initiative places strong emphasis on **technological innovation, digital infrastructure, and security**, positioning Microsoft as a central actor in shaping the continent's digital future.

In **June 2025**, Microsoft unveiled an additional plan focused on the “**preservation of Europe's digital sovereignty**.” While the company's narrative stresses cooperation and shared values with European institutions, these announcements reflect an increasing **technological framing of digital governance**, moving away from regulatory or societal perspectives. Microsoft's strategy appears to indicate a **partial withdrawal from compliance with certain aspects of the Digital Services Act (DSA)**, while simultaneously promoting a discourse of commitment to Europe under messages such as “*deepening our relationship with Europe*” or “*Europe can count on us*.” This communicative repositioning suggests an effort to **redefine its engagement with European regulators** on its own terms, emphasising technological partnership over legal accountability.

The company also seems to be **balancing transatlantic interests**, seeking to maintain its position as a trusted technological partner for both the **European Union**

⁴ Subscription Document for Microsoft Bing Ireland Unlimited Company. Available at <https://disinfocode.eu/subscriptionsforms/microsoft-bing1757573996.pdf>

and the United States, without fully aligning with either side’s policy agendas. At the same time, Microsoft has presented itself as a guarantor of **“digital stability”** for Europe, while reportedly considering **legal actions** to safeguard its continued involvement in the continent’s digital infrastructure.

Finally, it is worth noting that **topics such as media literacy, disinformation, and collaboration with civil society**, central to Commitment 17 of the Code of Practice on Disinformation, are **absent** from Microsoft’s recent communications. This absence reinforces the perception that the company’s current approach prioritises technological and market considerations over social and democratic responsibilities in the European digital ecosystem.

6. Deep assessment for the signatory TikTok

6.1. Media Context: How did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover TikTok's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

During the first half of 2025, Spanish media coverage of TikTok reflected **growing concern about the platform's role in algorithmic manipulation and the spread of disinformation**. While TikTok remains a formal signatory to the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**, media reports indicate a **lack of transparency in political processes**, **weak media literacy efforts**, and **an absence of coordinated educational and institutional initiatives**. All of which suggests a **violation of Article 17**, which requires concrete actions to promote public awareness and digital resilience.

The most relevant headlines on TikTok in Portugal and Spanish dailies

1. **“UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital”** (*UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital*). Source: Poder360br. February 14th 2025. The EU announced on 13 February 2025 that the Code of Practice on Disinformation will be integrated into the Digital Services Act (DSA). **The updated framework introduces measures to reduce financial incentives for spreading false information and to strengthen transparency in political advertising**, according to EFE. Participation remains voluntary, but compliance will now be subject to audits. **Since 2018, forty-two companies have joined the initiative, including Google, Meta, Microsoft, and TikTok. Elon Musk's platform X remains the only central platform not participating.**
2. **“Bruselas investiga a TikTok por injerencia en elecciones en Rumanía”** (*Brussels investigates TikTok over alleged interference in Romanian elections*). Source: *El País*, January 7, 2025. **The European Commission has launched an investigation into TikTok (owned by ByteDance) following evidence of information manipulation and disinformation during Romania's presidential elections**, which were annulled after coordinated, misleading campaigns were discovered on the platform. Although TikTok has signed the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation, the case raises doubts about its ability to detect and prevent political interference. **Brussels emphasised that the company is obliged to implement transparency measures and media literacy initiatives to prevent such electoral manipulation.**
3. **“Europa debe fijar un modelo de negocio que priorice el bienestar de los usuarios sobre la rentabilidad económica”** (*Europe must design a business model that puts users' well-being before profit*). Source: *El País*, February 17, 2025 – Opinion piece by Enrique Goñi (*Fundación Hermes*). **The article**

advocates establishing international regulatory frameworks to limit the power of major platforms, including TikTok and other algorithm-driven networks, to combat disinformation and protect younger audiences. It stresses the importance of investing in education and media literacy programs to counter fake news, algorithmic misinformation, and AI-generated content. The author advocates an approach grounded in **ethics, transparency, and public-private collaboration**, aligning with the goals of Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice.

4. **“Una imagen que vale mil engaños” (An image worth a thousand lies).** Source: *El País*, February 2025. This feature highlights the rapid spread of manipulated visual content on TikTok, driven by the rise of generative artificial intelligence. **The story highlights that the platform lacks practical tools for visual verification and fails to label synthetic or AI-generated content clearly.** The absence of educational initiatives and cooperation with public institutions contradicts the spirit of Article 17, which requires active measures to enhance digital literacy and critical awareness.

TikTok's main alerts on Code violations

1. **Political manipulation and lack of electoral transparency**

The European Commission's investigation into **TikTok's role in Romania** exposes **serious weaknesses in identifying and curbing coordinated disinformation campaigns.**

Brussels warns that the platform has **not demonstrated sufficient control over the spread of misleading political content.**

2. **Weak implementation of media literacy (Article 17)**

During the first half of 2025, **TikTok did not report any major educational or awareness campaigns in Spain** to help users identify or combat disinformation.

Article 17 requires proactive cooperation and training, yet the platform relies heavily on **self-regulation** with minimal public engagement.

3. **Risks from AI-Generated content**

The surge of **synthetic videos and deepfakes** on TikTok has raised alarm due to the **lack of mandatory labelling and user education** on how to detect manipulated media.

Experts warn that this gap **increases users' vulnerability to visual disinformation**, particularly among young audiences.

4. **Insufficient institutional cooperation**

TikTok has **not maintained consistent collaboration with public or educational institutions** in Spain to promote media literacy, thereby violating the **principles of cooperation and accountability** outlined in the EU Code of Practice.

After examining how Spanish- and Portuguese-language outlets framed **Commitment 17**, the table below outlines TikTok's performance in meeting the CoP's requirements.

Table 3. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: TikTok

Signatory: TikTok	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	3- good
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	2- adequate
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	4- good
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	4- good

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: 1- poor, 2- adequate, 3- good.

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: 1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.

6.2. Quality of response assessment

Regarding Commitment 17, TikTok indicates that it has implemented new measures. Among these, they report **three new ongoing general media literacy and critical thinking skills campaigns**. These campaigns are carried out in collaboration with national fact-checkers and are added to the initiatives already reported in previous reports. In this way, the platform has 14 media literacy campaigns across European states, including Spain and Portugal. The campaigns, however, are listed without description and are developed on- and off-platform media literacy campaigns

Related to elections, they identify **nine temporary media literacy integrity campaigns and seven Election Speaker Series sessions** (including one in Portugal with Polígrafo). They also include the launch of the Global Election Hub, which provides data on videos removed in the preceding weeks by country, as well as ongoing work in each local context (<https://www.tiktok.com/transparency/en-us/global-election-hub>).

TikTok also describes initiatives for specific topics arising in national contexts, **such as elections, armed conflicts, or climate change** (TikTok has expanded the Verified for Climate initiative, now including Spain among other countries). Besides, they report

specific initiatives, such as the revamped Holocaust Education Campaign and two new temporary search guides on **sensitive content**. **They also report addressing specific topics in some countries, including an action in Portugal regarding Pope Francis's health, and providing authoritative** information sources when events are unfolding rapidly, also in the context of natural disasters (outside the EU).

Regarding **in-app interventions**, the signatory reports **improvements in the Safety Center and Transparency Center**, as well as promoting training and development for moderation teams. They continue strengthening Integrity and Authenticity policies and expanding in-app measures, which now cover 23 official EU languages. They work with external experts to combat harmful misinformation (for example, the WHO). They use video notice tags to invite users to explore critical topics further and report new actions, including video tags, search interventions that redirect users searching for a topic towards authoritative sources, and in-app information centres.

The signatory does not respond regarding new measures planned for the next six months to mature the implementation of this commitment.

6.3. Verification of reported information

The signatory presents **quantitative data on impressions, clicks, and click-through rate for measures** as state media labels, video notices, or search interventions related to misinformation/denial of the Holocaust, mpox, elections, or climate change. These specific actions include data, but others lack evidence regarding engagement metrics or participants.

Additionally, TikTok provides quantitative data with the same characteristics for general media literacy and critical thinking skills campaigns (including Spain in partnership with Maldita and Portugal with Polígrafo).

Some measures, such as promoting election integrity, include links and screenshots of actions in specific countries (for example, Portugal). Likewise, particular measures such as Verified for Climate reference other evidence, such as 108,000 responses to a user survey or millions of people reached by media literacy campaigns (excluding Spain and Portugal).

Therefore, a predominance of quantitative data is identified. In addition to impressions and engagement metrics, they have included some additional evidence. However, they should continue strengthening accountability for all activities, including their impact, and providing a more precise description of the activities.

6.4. Evaluation of actions taken

They present **relevant actions to strengthen media literacy and critical thinking skills, as well as measures addressing specific topics**. The quantitative data indicate a seemingly significant volume of impacts; **however, their effectiveness is difficult to assess (the click-through rate is very low)**. Only one of the actions is

reported to have some outputs (the climate change search intervention tool is available in 23 official EU languages, plus Norwegian and Icelandic for EEA users). It redirects users looking for climate change-related content to authoritative sources and encourages them to report any potential misinformation they encounter. Given that hashtags related to climate change (such as #ClimateChange, #SustainableLiving, and #ClimateAction) have more than 1.2 million associated posts on TikTok, this is a valuable initiative.

The quantitative data provided may appear high in terms of impressions, but the click-through rate is very low. Looking at Spain and Portugal, **it does not reach 0.50%, which makes the effectiveness of the reported measures questionable**—except for “Search interventions (Holocaust Misinformation/Denial)”, where Portugal shows a click-through rate of 11.02% and Spain 10.43%, although with very low impressions (11,758 in Portugal, 390,281 in Spain).

Overall, we must acknowledge limitations in properly assessing the effectiveness of the actions with the available data.

- **General campaigns: 3.**

- **Specific campaigns: 5.** The more concrete the action to promote media literacy, the more efficient the effort. The question is whether the issues selected are actually the core of the disinformation campaigns. Some actions, such as sensitive content or rapidly unfolding events, neutralise the foreseeable harm caused by a particular act of disinformation. Others, such as combating disinformation about disasters, are significant in situations of uncertainty, where information is key to safety and the restoration of normality.

- Elections: 5
- Holocaust: 5
- Sensitive content and events unfolded rapidly: 5
- Disasters: 5

- **Other actions: 5.** These actions create a consciousness among users about the risk of disinformation and the need for tools for combating it in the day-by-day online navigation. Lastly, training human moderation teams is very relevant to identifying and, consequently, eliminating disinformation.

- In-app interventions: 5
- Creation of networks Verified Climate and Verified Champions: 5
- Supporting mental well-being awareness and literacy, and to combat misinformation with reliable content through the WHO's Fides network: 5
- AI authenticity campaigns: 5
- Initiatives for transparency, mainly addressed to elections: 5
- Investing in training and development for the human moderation teams: 5

On the other hand, this report highlights several collaborative actions with fact-checkers, although we believe there is room to expand cooperation with the hubs and other hub partners.

They state that they work with “an array of industry experts, non-governmental organizations, and industry associations around the world.” In this report, they explicitly refer to a partner from IBERIFIER Plus: Polígrafo, in Portugal. However, there are no specific actions with the hub under Commitment 17.

6.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

- **Strength accountability** for all activities, including their impact, and providing a more precise description of the activities.
- **Design initiatives to boost the impact of media literacy activities**, as click-through rates are very low.
- Exploring the possibility of **opening up cooperation with EDMO hubs** specifically for boosting the commitment 17.

7. Deep assessment for the signatory Facebook

7.1. Media Context: How did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover YouTube's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

Between January and June 2025, Spanish media coverage of **Facebook (Meta)** revealed a **progressive retreat from its commitments under the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**. The **removal of independent fact-checkers** and the **lack of media literacy programs** point to an evident **violation of Article 17**. The rise in **fraud on Facebook Marketplace** further underscores Meta's **failure to protect users and promote digital education**. Overall, Meta is portrayed as **increasingly resistant to European regulation**, prioritising profitability and operational freedom over its **social and informational responsibilities**.

The most relevant headlines on Facebook in Portugal and Spanish dailies:

1. **“Facebook, Instagram e WhatsApp lideram queixas sobre serviços digitais em Portugal”** (*Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp lead complaints about digital services in Portugal*). Source: Tek Notícias, Sapó. June 16th 2025. In the first quarter of the year, **ANACOM received 27 complaints about digital services, half of which targeted Meta platforms—Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp**. Facebook accounted for 30% of all complaints. According to ANACOM, 67% of complaints concerned unjustified suspensions, restrictions, or account or content removals. Illegal-content reports represented 19%, while 11% concerned customer support or points of contact.
2. **“UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital”** (*UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital*). Source: Poder360br. February 14th 2025. The EU announced on 13 February 2025 that the Code of Practice on Disinformation will be integrated into the Digital Services Act (DSA). **The updated framework introduces measures to reduce financial incentives for spreading false information and to strengthen transparency in political advertising**, according to EFE. Participation remains voluntary, but compliance will now be subject to audits. **Since 2018, forty-two companies have joined the initiative, including Meta. Elon Musk's platform X remains the only central platform not participating.**
3. **“Meta elimina los verificadores de contenido en Facebook, Instagram y WhatsApp”** (*Meta removes fact-checkers from Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp*). Source: *La Razón*, January 9, 2025. The story explains that Meta **has terminated its partnerships with independent fact-checkers** and replaced them with an internal system similar to X's (formerly Twitter) *Community Notes*. This move represents a **significant setback** in Meta's commitment to the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**, particularly in

terms of verification and transparency. By removing external verification, Meta **weakens mechanisms for combating disinformation**. The company **shifts the responsibility to users**, reducing content quality control and **contradicting the intent of Article 17**, which emphasises collaboration and media literacy as tools against misinformation.

4. **“Europa debe fijar un modelo de negocio que priorice el bienestar de los usuarios sobre la rentabilidad económica” (Europe must set a business model that prioritizes users’ well-being over profit)**. Source: *El País*, February 17, 2025. Opinion piece by Enrique Goñi (*Fundación Hermes*). This article denounces the **growing impunity of big tech companies**, including Meta, for **removing content verification mechanisms** and justifying it under the guise of “freedom of expression.” It highlights that **Meta (Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp) and X** have both **reduced independent fact-checking efforts**, weakening the fight against misinformation. The piece warns that these actions **erode democratic safeguards** and risk breaching commitments under the EU’s disinformation framework. It calls for stronger **media literacy, ethical standards, and transparency**, which are core obligations outlined in **Article 17** of the Code of Practice.
5. **“Facebook Market es la principal fuente de fraudes online en Reino Unido” (Facebook Marketplace is now the primary source of online scams in the UK)**. Source: *Expansión*, May 11, 2025. A financial report warns that **Facebook Marketplace has become the leading platform for online fraud** in the UK, according to the banking sector. Around **72% of digital scams originate online**, with Facebook Marketplace identified as **“the main source of problems.”** Banks and regulators are urging **tech companies to take stricter measures** to detect and prevent scams. The situation highlights significant **shortcomings in consumer protection and digital literacy**, violating **Article 17**, which emphasises the need for active cooperation and user education.

Main alerts on code violations

1. Elimination of independent verification

Meta’s decision to end cooperation with external fact-checking organisations is a **direct breach of its transparency and collaboration commitments** under the Code.

The consequence is a **proliferation of false and misleading information**, especially on topics such as politics, migration, and gender.

2. Invoking “Freedom of Expression” as a defence

Meta argues that EU verification requirements **limit political debate**, but the media interpret this as an attempt to **avoid accountability**.

This stance **undermines the balance** between freedom of speech and the fight against disinformation that the Code seeks to establish.

3. Fraud risks on the Facebook marketplace

Recurring scams highlight **the platform's inadequate oversight of commercial and advertising content**, resulting in economic losses and a decline in public trust.

Regulators have called for **greater cooperation and user education**, as required by Article 17.

4. Deficit in media literacy (Article 17)

During the first half of 2025, **IBERIFIER researchers identified no new initiatives from Meta or Facebook in Spain** aimed at promoting digital education or critical thinking.

This represents a **clear violation of Article 17**, which requires platforms to collaborate with governments and NGOs to strengthen media literacy.

After examining how Spanish- and Portuguese-language outlets framed Commitment 17, the table below outlines Facebook's performance in meeting the requirements of the CoP.

Table 4. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Facebook

Signatory: Facebook	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	<i>1- poor</i>
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	<i>1- poor</i>
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	<i>1- very poor</i>
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	<i>1- very poor</i>

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: *1- poor, 2- adequate, 3- good.*

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: *1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.*

7.2. Quality of response assessment

Reporting has become extremely generic, even low-effort. Not only does the platform show no relevant changes, but it also appears to be unmotivated to improve the situation. **The negative aspects of previous reporting have become more salient, and some positive elements, such as KPIs and indicator data, which we deemed insufficient during the last evaluation, are now entirely gone.** Overall, information about Facebook reporting has worsened compared to previous reporting. Evaluation dropped from adequate to poor.

The report outlines a strategy structured around user-oriented tools (warning screens, verified badges on Facebook, and notifications for outdated articles) and initiatives such as awareness campaigns on Youth well-being (Ireland, France, Spain, Italy, and the Netherlands) and global anti-scam campaigns, based on tools available to users. However, **those platform features were already reported in the previous report (using the exact words) without providing any metrics on their impact.** They do provide some generic information for the countries as a whole: 555M impressions, 92,9M users reached outside Meta's channels, and a total of 2,5 billion impressions (estimation).

Meta also mentions the publication of a "Media Literacy Annual Plan", which outlines the company's approach to media literacy via the products and features that are available to Facebook and Instagram users. **We could not consult the plan, which the company claims is public,** and therefore cannot assess its content or purpose. Oddly, such a central document wouldn't be displayed in this reporting exercise, given its centrality to the plan.

Facebook maintains its procedures during national elections, providing Election Day voting information and promoting credible information about the process. They highlight examples from the German federal election and the Polish presidential election in Poland (top-of-the-feed notifications directing people to credible official sources). They do mention the 2025 snap general election in Portugal, highlighting the same procedures as in Poland and Germany, **but provide no data on the reach and effectiveness of measures.**

META does not collaborate with IBERIFIER Plus, and the description of partnerships is generic (experts, educators, civic society, and governments) with no detail about the core of these partnerships. They mention national ministries, fact-checkers (they collaborate with Polígrafo in Portugal, but this is not mentioned in the reporting), and other organisations such as UNESCO.

7.3. Verification of reported information

Quality of reporting has worsened, data-wise. **The data provided in previous reports**

was scarce, and in this report, any mention of impressions, reach, or user actions is gone. First of all, Facebook reports the Media Literacy Annual Plan; however, it is unclear what the content is or how it has been distributed. In addition, we couldn't find it, even though it was published by the end of July. There is no data related to the impact of its implementation.

The report also mentions campaigns aimed at raising awareness of Meta products, especially Fraud & Scams, which provide users with context. However, **the lack of data on user engagement and limited visibility on outcomes specific to Spain and Portugal undermines effectiveness.** There is a lack of detail on the metrics; in addition, this campaign has not been developed in Portugal (only in Spain, France, the Netherlands and Italy). The metrics offered (reach, views, and engagement) are combined across all three countries (not broken down by country).

Tools as "outdated article notifications" or "verified badges" support media literacy passively but are not integrated with impact measurement.

The actions related to national elections mainly consist of notifications in the feed that remind citizens of the day and direct them to the national authoritative institutions. Meta also proactively promoted reliable information about elections by creating in-app "Voter Information Units (VIU) and "Election Day Information" reminders (EDR). Each tool reached 4.6 million and 3.3 million users in Portugal. However, **this data lacks context to assess its impact. It would be necessary to complement it with context on how users interact with the information,** including metrics such as one-minute interaction rates, watch time, organic reach, etc. Facebook provides these metrics to the administrators of its pages, so it is noteworthy that it does not offer this data for the campaigns it describes.

Regarding **the Youth campaign, it is unclear how it will help users improve their media literacy skills, as it aims to promote** mental well-being by offering tools to reduce screen time.

Regarding the partnership, **there is no data on the number of initiatives or the detailed actions developed.** Action partnerships seem valuable (they include universities, fact-checkers, and governmental bodies), but there is a lack of detail on which governments and the kinds of agreements they have developed.

7.4. Evaluation of actions taken

Meta has deployed a wide range of tools that support media literacy by informing users about the credibility of content (e.g., verified badges and warnings for outdated articles). Campaigns focused on fraud and digital literacy reached a broad audience. However, **the lack of localised or interactive interventions limits their transformative potential in Iberian contexts.** All the initiatives have a centralised focus, not adapted to the national contexts where some specific misinformation

campaigns may arise.

For the reasons listed above (poor reporting and metrics), it is not possible to assess the initiative's effectiveness, nor is there any relevant information regarding its specific impact in Spain and Portugal. Impressions are an insufficient KPI in this instance. **There appears to be some reach for said initiatives, but there is little to no granularity in reported data, between and within countries.**

7.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

- Overall, the **initiatives and campaigns described appear centralised** and not adapted to local media literacy needs. Facebook should adjust its actions to the Iberian context.
- The **Media Literacy Annual Plan should be made public** or, at least, explained thoroughly so evaluators could assess its impact.
- Facebook should **provide metrics so evaluators can assess the real impact of the actions performed**—such as engagement rate, publication reach, click-through rates, views of specific content, etc.
- Facebook should also **report its partnerships with national/local entities, diversify them (e.g., fact-checkers, academic institutions, public entities), and provide metrics** on the impact of its cooperation initiatives.

8. Deep assessment for the signatory Instagram

8.1. Media context: how did outlets in Portugal and Spain cover YouTube's commitment under Article 17 of the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation?

During the first half of 2025, Spanish media coverage of Instagram and Meta consistently pointed to a **growing divergence from the commitments outlined in the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**. While Meta defends its approach as a means to protect free expression, its **decision to abolish independent fact-checking** and neglect its media literacy obligations has been widely interpreted as a breach of Article 17, thereby undermining the public's capacity to recognise and resist misinformation.

The most relevant headlines on Instagram in Portugal and Spanish dailies

1. **4. “Facebook, Instagram e WhatsApp lideram queixas sobre serviços digitais em Portugal”** (*Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp lead complaints about digital services in Portugal*). Source: Tek Notícias, Sapo. June 16th 2025. In the first quarter of the year, 15% of **complaints about digital services** received were related to Instagram (15%).
2. **5. “UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital”** (*UE inclui código voluntário contra fake news em lei digital*). Source: Poder360br. February 14th 2025. The EU announced on 13 February 2025 that the Code of Practice on Disinformation will be integrated into the Digital Services Act (DSA). **The updated framework introduces measures to reduce financial incentives for spreading false information and to strengthen transparency in political advertising**, according to EFE. Participation remains voluntary, but compliance will now be subject to audits. **Since 2018, forty-two companies have joined the initiative, including Meta.**
3. **“Meta elimina los verificadores de contenido en Facebook, Instagram y WhatsApp”** (*Meta removes content fact-checkers on Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp*). Source: *La Razón*, January 9, 2025. The story warns that Meta's decision to **eliminate independent fact-checking programs** represents a serious **step backwards** in its commitment to the **EU Code of Practice on Disinformation**. In their place, Meta will introduce **“Community Notes”**, a system inspired by X (formerly Twitter), which leaves content verification in the hands of users. **Identified risk:** this change **weakens disinformation control mechanisms** and could increase the spread of false content. **Impact on Article 17:** It undermines media literacy efforts by shifting verification responsibility to untrained users.
4. **“Europa debe fijar un modelo de negocio que priorice el bienestar de los**

usuarios sobre la rentabilidad económica” (*Europe must build a business model that puts user well-being ahead of profits*). Source: *El País*, February 17, 2025 – Opinion piece by Enrique Goñi (Fundación Hermes). The piece criticises the **impunity of major tech companies**, including Meta (Instagram), for **weakening content verification** and **evading accountability** in tackling disinformation. It notes that **both Meta and X have “removed independent fact-checkers”**, threatening the integrity of the EU’s disinformation code. Meta justifies the decision as a defence of “freedom of expression,” while misinformation and hate speech continue to grow. The author calls for stronger **digital education and media literacy initiatives**, which are core obligations under Article 17, to counter algorithmic manipulation and online deception.

5. **“Una imagen que vale mil engaños”** (*An image worth a thousand lies*). Source: *El País*, February 2025. This feature examines how **manipulated images and deceptive visual content are proliferating on Instagram**, particularly through **AI-generated media**. It highlights the **lack of practical image verification tools** and the **absence of clear labelling for AI-generated content**. The report warns that the **failure to promote educational initiatives** and the **lack of cooperation with public bodies** run counter to the principles set out in **Article 17** of the EU Code.

Main alerts regarding code violations

1. Withdrawal of independent fact-checkers

Meta (Instagram) has **discontinued collaboration with external fact-checking organisations**. This **contradicts the Code’s commitments to transparency and cooperation** with trusted information actors. As a result, a higher risk of **unchecked false information spreading across the platform**.

2. Delegating fact-checking to users (“Community Notes”)

Although presented as a “democratic” solution, experts warn it **lacks professional rigour and reinforces group bias**. It marks a **setback for media literacy**, replacing structured education and critical thinking with unverified user opinion.

3. Absence of media literacy campaigns (Article 17)

Researchers in Spain identified no proactive initiatives by Meta or Instagram during the first half of 2025 aimed at promoting **digital education or critical media awareness**. This represents a **failure to meet Article 17 obligations**, which call for collaboration among platforms, governments, and civil society to strengthen resilience against disinformation.

4. Using “freedom of expression” as a justification

Both *La Razón* and *El País* report that Meta **invokes freedom of speech to deflect accountability** for harmful or misleading content, reflecting a broader global trend toward **deregulation**.

After examining how Spanish- and Portuguese-language outlets framed Commitment 17, the table below outlines Instagram's performance in meeting the requirements of the CoP.

Table 5. Analysis of Assessment Commitment 17: Instagram

<i>Signatory: Instagram</i>	
Section	Score
1. Quality and Completeness Documentation of media literacy actions	<i>1- poor</i>
2. Evidence Provision of supporting data for listed actions	<i>1- poor</i>
3. Impact Impact of media literacy actions	<i>2- poor</i>
4. Rating Effectiveness of media literacy actions	<i>1- very poor</i>

*Scale of scores for sections 1 and 2: *1- poor, 2- adequate, 3- good.*

*Scale of scores for sections 3 and 4: *1- very poor, 2- poor, 3- fair, 4- good, 5- excellent.*

8.2. Quality of response assessment

The report's quality is limited by the lack of detail about the initiatives undertaken. Instagram mentions tools and resources, but does not elaborate on them.

Regarding **the youth mental health well-being campaign**, Meta launched in Spain, Italy, the Netherlands, and France, aimed at increasing awareness of tools available on Instagram to protect Youth mental health (privacy settings, verified accounts, limit reminders, and sleep mode). **The campaign is not detailed; it just describes the duration and mentions the platforms used** (8 weeks from January 13th 2025, across a range of channels, including Meta-owned channels, print, digital, audio, TV, and Outdoor), **so we can't assess whether it has been country-tailored.** In addition, Portugal has not been specifically addressed. On top of that, it is unclear how this initiative can help increase users' media literacy.

The **global anti-scam awareness campaign** (romance scams/targeting scammers) **is not detailed**; in fact, apart from the link to a blog post in the Meta website, there are no specific initiatives in the Iberian context, nor any explanation of how they reach particular targets.

Regarding **the features developed, Meta mentions warming screens on sensitive content on Instagram.** However, they fall short in explaining the overall strategy behind these actions. Besides, it is not clear how limiting the visibility of specific posts

containing sensitive material can boost users' media literacy skills, nor how it can help fight disinformation.

Verified badges help users feel confident about the accounts they interact with. Especially relevant for avoiding impersonation. The initiative seems valuable; however, **the reports fall short in providing the global strategy or metrics for assessing the real impact**, for instance, how many users asked for verified badges, how many were accepted, how many accounts have been removed due to impersonation claims, etc.

Lastly, they have developed "In-app Election Day Information" in Germany, Poland and Portugal, it consists of notices at the top of the feed on Instagram, reminding people of the day they can vote and redirecting them to national authoritative sources on how and where to vote. Election Day: with a description of the particular task or functions that Instagram designed.

8.3. Verification of reported information

The **data provided is not detailed enough to assess the impact in Spain or Portugal, as these countries are mentioned, but the figures are aggregated with those of other countries.** For example, in the Youth campaign, the data provided is not detailed by country nor differentiated by platform (Facebook and Instagram). The only metrics offered are reach and impressions, both within and outside the platform. However, reach and impressions do not indicate how people interacted with the information, as there is no data on whether users read the content, shared it with their contacts, or commented on it.

Regarding the national election actions in Portugal, Instagram offers just two quantitative metrics: Voter Information Unit (VIU) reach 5.2 million, and Election Day Reminder (EDR) reach 4.3 million. It would be helpful to get metrics on how users interacted with the content and the initiatives developed, to assess whether the initiatives were sufficient or should be complemented with other measures. As it is not detailed, **it is not possible to evaluate whether, apart from the feature described, any other actions tailored to country needs or to the specific and controversial topics arising during the election campaign were performed.**

Finally, **regarding other initiatives** (tools implemented or videos and content aimed at teaching how to detect misleading information), **META does not offer any metrics on their impact, such as reach, interaction rate, etc.**

8.4. Evaluation of actions taken

The effectiveness of the applied media literacy action is considered very poor (1), since, **beyond adding a label to content or a banner linking to an official source, no active campaigns engaging users have been carried out.** The chosen

collaborations are good, but there is no evidence of initiative proliferation.

There are **no specific actions or campaigns tailored to the Iberian context**. The only specific initiative described is the response to the Portuguese parliamentary election. However, the data on the impact is scarce: there are no details about the actions or specific campaigns. The campaign described, addressed to young people, has not been developed in Portugal, only in Spain, France, the Netherlands and Italy, but there is no explanation for why the action is centred on those countries.

As noted in previous reports (see, for example, deliverable 5.2), **Meta should strengthen its national/local strategy by collaborating with local institutions to improve users' media literacy skills**. Meta describes its cooperation initiatives and agreements with international universities or organisations (such as UNESCO or the Micro:bit Foundation). Still, it lacks local-level cooperation, which would be essential to increase the impact of its strategy.

8.5. Recommendations/need for improvement

- **Develop initiatives tailored to Portugal and Spain's specific needs to boost media literacy in their contexts**, addressing their particular issues.
- To **collaborate with national associations in the Iberian context**, specialised in media literacy, to perform specific actions related to controversial topics within each country.
- Offer **detailed metrics of the campaigns reported** (click-through rate, impressions rate, relevance ratio of the information, reach of the action, etc.). Those are metrics available to any platform user; therefore, it seems feasible that Meta reports them for its own campaigns.
- **Some of the actions do not align with media literacy; if they do, Meta should explain how they help users and provide data to assess their real impact**. If not, Meta should remove those initiatives from the report of commitment 17.

9. Conclusions

The analysis of reports from **VLOPs and VLOSEs** indicates substantial disparities in engagement levels and the quality of information provided. In most cases, signatories have failed to provide sufficient data, measurable outcomes, or evidence-based evaluations of the actions they have undertaken.

Google Search and **YouTube** maintain partial compliance with the Code but continue to reproduce the same measures already reported in previous stages, showing minimal innovation or adaptation to the Iberian context. Their reports lack granularity and adequate performance metrics, limiting the ability to assess the real impact of their media literacy initiatives.

Meta platforms (Facebook and Instagram) have shown a significant regression by withdrawing from cooperation with independent fact-checkers and replacing external verification systems with user-driven mechanisms. These changes are inconsistent with the principles of transparency and collaboration established under the Code and undermine users' trust in the reliability of information.

TikTok demonstrates comparatively stronger engagement through a variety of media literacy campaigns and collaborations with fact-checking entities, including **Polígrafo** in Portugal. However, despite quantitative data on impressions and reach, the low click-through rates and limited qualitative evaluation raise doubts about the effectiveness and sustainability of these actions.

LinkedIn and **Bing**, both under Microsoft, formally opted out of Commitment 17 during this reporting period. Their justification, that the measures are not proportionate to their systemic risk profiles, illustrates a restrictive interpretation of the Code's objectives and a concerning reluctance to assume their educational and societal responsibilities.

Across all reports, the evidence suggests that most signatories prioritise corporate and regulatory self-interest over the social obligations inherent in the Code. This pattern reflects a growing detachment between **formal adherence** and **substantive implementation**, undermining the voluntary nature of the framework and calling for more substantial alignment with the **Digital Services Act (DSA)** obligations.

Findings from media monitoring

The media analysis conducted in **Portugal and Spain**, using **Google News** in Portugal and **Mynews database** in Spain, identified an intensified public debate around platform accountability, digital safety, and the EU's regulatory capacity, particularly in the Spanish case. Between January and June 2025, Iberian news outlets repeatedly covered issues such as Meta's withdrawal of verification measures, Google's

resistance to EU oversight, and the European Commission's investigations into TikTok's role in electoral processes. The tone of coverage was predominantly **critical**, underscoring widespread concern about disinformation risks and the erosion of user protections. Opinion pieces and editorials in leading dailies such as *El País*, *El Nacional*, *La Razón*, and *Expansión* in Spain, as well as *Rádio Renascença* and *Sapo Notícias* in Portugal, framed these developments as symptomatic of a deeper structural tension between freedom of expression, commercial interests, and democratic accountability.

In Portugal, media coverage of the topic is not only much scarcer than in Spain but also tends to be more generalist, **focusing heavily on platforms' lack of commitment to EU regulations** and on urgent topics such as disinformation. **We found no specific reference to Commitment 17 or to media literacy.** There is also attention being given to the topic in Brazil and in Brazilian Portuguese, with references to resistance from platforms in fulfilling EU regulations. **In these cases, the uniqueness of the EU's approach is noted, as is the behaviour of platforms in the EU context.** While the coverage of European digital regulation is favourable, the lack of depth underscores the need for measures to raise awareness of the reach and diversity of these regulations, as well as the broader societal goals they aim to achieve. **In the Portuguese context, this applies both to the EU and to the platforms themselves, which might use the regulatory context in a pedagogical way and for self-promotion, presenting their digital environments as safe, positive, and optimistic actors in the accomplishment of communitarian goals.**

In both countries, media discourse also revealed a growing demand for **binding regulatory mechanisms** to replace the CoP's voluntary, uneven compliance model. The inclusion of the Code of Practice within the DSA framework, as reported during the same period, has been widely perceived as an essential step to ensure legal enforceability and transparency in the digital ecosystem.

The overall assessment highlights the need for:

1. **Enhanced transparency and measurable indicators** in future reports to enable proper evaluation of the impact of media literacy initiatives.
2. **Stronger collaboration** between signatories and **national EDMO hubs**, such as IBERIFIER, to contextualise and implement media literacy actions at local and regional levels.
3. **Harmonised reporting frameworks** across all signatories to ensure comparability, accountability, and consistency in the interpretation of Commitment 17.
4. **Integration of voluntary commitments within legally binding instruments**, ensuring that platforms' societal obligations are aligned with the enforcement mechanisms established by the DSA.

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IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It is made up of thirteen universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyse the Iberian digital media ecosystem and address misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists and informants, young people and society as a whole.

For more information, please visit the project website at iberifier.eu

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